

The Effect of Recognition Language on Addictive Nature in The Use of Social Media

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ABSTRACT: Language of recognition is the act of retrieving existing knowledge, creates the possibility of seeing something or someone from a new perspective. The leading causes of addiction: the need to socialize, get pleasure, and get a sense of security and control over the situation. This research employs a mixed-methods approach with a sequential explanatory design. To analyze the data quantitatively, the author employs a simple linear regression test on the results of the questionnaire. Activities in qualitative data analysis include reducing data, presenting data, and verifying data. Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that the desire for recognition from others has led social media users in Jakarta to become addicted to social media. This finding was further supported by an interview with Praz Teguh, a social media activist and a celebrity. He acknowledged that many social media users use social media as a platform to seek recognition.

KEYWORDS: Addiction, Mixed method, Recognition language, Recognition, Social media.

INTRODUCTION

Language has become a crucial element in today's world. It is not only a tool for communication between people, but it also serves several other functions. Beyond communication, language serves as a unifying tool, such as Indonesian, the national language. Using Indonesian in inter-ethnic communication fosters effective communication. Language serves not only as a unifying tool but also as a tool for recognition. This tool is used to assess the extent to which a topic or issue under discussion is perceived as good or bad by society. This process is initially conducted through a reflective process.

Social media has become a significant influence on people's lives today. It is not only used as a tool for long-distance communication between individuals or groups, but also as a platform for people to express their feelings or experiences. Unfortunately, social media can also be a destructive tool for communities and even nations. Social media has been misused. Many individuals use social media as a platform for insults, mental harm, and other negative things, rather than as a platform for appreciation.

When using social media, people use it not only to save photos of special moments but also to express themselves through language. Language is inseparable from social media because it serves as a tool for expressing oneself, regardless of whether those statements are positive or negative. This makes language a tool for expressing itself addictively. Even individuals who were not initially active social media users can be influenced to become active users. Unfortunately, the original purpose of social media has shifted due to the language used within it.

As moral subjects and agents, humans, in every relationship of recognition, always require attention, respect, and self-confidence to build relationships with others in various forms and spaces of life. This relationship of recognition cannot be returned entirely to a model of human relations that solely emphasizes the satisfaction of self-interest as a social actor. Instead, a model of human relations is needed that is characterized in and through relationships with others. Ethical subjects and agents depend on the ability to respond to others with attention to their needs and emotions, respect their moral and legal dignity, and believe in their social success.

In living life and building relationships with others, an individual needs some form of recognition that can generate respect and admiration from others. This dependence on recognition is what drives people to constantly seek and demand recognition from others. Social media is currently used as a means to gain recognition from others. Unfortunately, this recognition, both positive and negative, creates a sense of dependency and addiction. People feel that a lack of recognition from others makes life meaningless or lacking

The above factors prompted the researchers to conduct this study. Therefore, the researchers concluded that the research question was: What is the relationship between recognition language and addictive behaviour in social media use? This study examines the

relationship between recognition language and addiction in social media use.

Etymologically, recognition means 'to discover' or 'to know something or someone again', derived from the Latin verb *cognōscere*, meaning to know, and the prefix *re*. According to this etymology, recognition means the act of gaining knowledge again, which opens up the possibility of seeing someone we encounter in our daily lives in a new light, with "new eyes." Recognition is a kind of "detour" in the cycle of human sociality.

Gadamer as cited in Runesi (Runesi, 2015), demonstrates that a dialogue within the mind is taking place during the process of thinking, and this illustrates a close connection with language. This is why Gadamer argued that human experience should also be understood as linguistic. Chomsky expressed the same point in his article on Runesi (Runesi, 2015) He argued that a system of knowledge should exist within each person's mind that enables them to communicate effectively. Therefore, he stated that many linguistic elements or grammatical rules are ingrained in humans. Both demonstrate that something always precedes the act of knowing: a natural capacity for language.

Recognition as a social grammar can be interpreted analogously in light of the thinking of Gadamer and Chomsky presented above. Recognition as a social grammar means that socially, humans have an innate capacity to be directed toward others. This means that specific rules precede, which create the potential for a social group to build togetherness and motivate subjects to accept others in their lives. In general, a husband, for example, will automatically recognize a baby born to his wife as his own. Thus, the character of the subject is always individual and social, and its grammar is recognition, which sometimes must be fought for. Everyone is always drawn to be recognized and to acknowledge other subjects who have the same rights, who can develop and realize themselves in society.

Therefore, according to Honneth, to achieve full autonomy, every subject requires a space for recognition in society (Fajarni, 2022). The two main premises underlying his belief in the importance of recognition for the subject are, first, regarding the subject's autonomy, recognition has substantially the same meaning and breadth as self-realization. Second, the premise of intersubjectivity, namely that the structured subject depends on its social membership as a support for self-realization (Fajarni, 2022). The forms of recognition above serve as constitutive standards for the 'health' of social relations when faced with various forms of social pathology.

Recognition as an acknowledgement of the 'other' is manifested in three forms of recognition, namely: love, law, and solidarity (Meitikasari & Drianus, 2021) These three forms are used to achieve wholeness. Wholeness is realized through personal freedom to determine one's desires (self-realization) and develop in a good life (ethical life). Recognition, therefore, presupposes knowledge and reflection on reciprocal relationships based on human multidimensionality (Meitikasari & Drianus, 2021).

Meanwhile, according to Pariyatman et al., (Pariyatman et al., 2022), Honneth articulates and systematises Hegel and Mead's thinking on three types of social conditions that constitute the normative prerequisites for subjective autonomy at the level of recognition. First, affective life is protected within the intimate sphere of love; second, the subject can see himself as equal to everyone else, as a legally complete subject; and third, the subject can see that his contribution to social life is recognized or valued (Fajarni, 2022). These three types can be distinguished based on the direction of meaning in achieving goals. Love is referred to as a medium for recognition; law is a form that enables self-realization, and solidarity holds the potential for the development of social morality in society.

Honneth attempts to investigate the "moral grammar" of social conflict within institutions and social relations, which has been characteristic of modern society since his early work (*The Critique of Power*). From this "moral grammar" perspective, Honneth rejects the view that social conflict is a fundamental element of human phenomena, rooted in the self-interest of each individual (Runesi, 2015).

Such a view, according to Honneth, is rooted in Hobbes's view that humans are essentially self-interested creatures, namely, to preserve and defend themselves, by seeking pleasure and avoiding pain, in a conception that seems to have had a brilliant influence on contemporary political philosophy. Such a conception, of course, radically rejects the more balanced view that states humans can only develop in groups, as in Aristotle's thinking about political humans.

By placing the dimension of "recognition" as the primary one in building social relations, Honneth expressed his belief that prioritising interpersonal relations over instrumental actions opens up the possibility for each speaker involved to express themselves to their communication partners (Fajarni, 2022). As human individuals, based on their perspectives, humans will be driven to

recognize other individuals as equal subjects with the right to develop and engage in self-development. Honneth's position, when compared to Habermas's, whose critical theory emphasizes the development of the subject's argumentative capacity, focuses more on the conditions for the subject's interaction with other subjects. Honneth wants to show that recognition is a necessary condition (sine qua non) for the morality of the subject or social agent (as social grammar). Recognition as a moral act becomes the *conditio sine qua non* for intersubjective relations.

Yuniarti, Engkus, and Hikmat (2017), as cited in (Sabekti et al., 2019), stated that teenagers strive to appear as attractive as possible in order to gain recognition and attraction. Secsio, Putri, Nurwati, & S (2016) in Sabekti et al. (Sabekti et al., 2019), social media is addictive for teenagers; the more active they are, the cooler and more sociable they become. Social media offers a variety of features, allowing users to freely and enjoyably document their experiences. Frequently uploading photos or videos can hinder optimal personal development (Sabekti et al., 2019).

Research by Rahardjo et al., (Rahardjo et al., 2020), a study on social media addiction, such as WhatsApp and Instagram, in adolescents. It shows that two roles of Instagram are the leading causes of addiction, namely the need to socialize and get pleasure. Four roles of WhatsApp are the leading causes of addiction, namely the need to be able to do many things, socialize, get pleasure, and get a sense of security and control the situation. Sifa and Sawitri (Sifa & Sawitri, 2018) examined the relationship between Instagram social media addiction and self-regulation. The results showed a negative relationship between the level of addiction and self-regulation, where the higher the level of self-regulation, the lower the potential for addiction, and vice versa. Soliha (2015), as cited in Rismala et al., (Rismala et al., 2021), concluded that there was a positive relationship of 31.4% between the level of dependence of social media users and social anxiety.

Kuss & Griffiths (2011), in the article by Santoso et al., (Santoso et al., 2022), the rapid increase in social media use, particularly about the increased amount of time people spend online, has led some to claim that excessive social media use may be addictive for some individuals. Excessive internet or mass media use can have both physical and mental impacts. Research conducted by Widya et al., as reported in an article by Sakinah et al., (Sakinah et al., 2019), indicates that accessing social media is positively associated with insomnia. The more intense the social media use, the higher the level of insomnia experienced. Someone who spends a long time using social media can become dependent or addicted (Sakinah et al., 2019).

Griffiths (2011) in the article Khairun and Hakim (Khairun & Hakim, 2021), individuals can be said to use social media with high intensity or even become addicted if they fulfill the following aspects of addiction: A. Salience (importance); This occurs when internet use becomes the most important activity in an individual's life, dominating the individual's thoughts (preoccupation or cognitive impairment), feelings (feeling overwhelmingly needy), and behaviour (deterioration in social behaviour). The individual will always think about the internet, even when not actively using it. B. Mood modification (mood changes); This leads to the individual's own experiences being the result of playing the internet, and can be seen as a coping strategy.

C. Tolerance: This is a process where the number of internet users increases, having a changing effect on the heart. D. Withdrawal Symptoms: This is an unpleasant feeling that occurs because internet use is reduced or discontinued (e.g., irritability, anxiety, or tremors). E. Conflict; This leads to conflicts that occur between internet users and their surroundings (interpersonal conflicts), conflicts in other tasks (work, assignments, social life, hobbies), or conflicts that occur within oneself (intrapersonal conflicts or feeling a lack of control), resulting from spending too much time playing on the internet.

F. Relapse: This is a tendency for internet usage patterns to recur after controls are in place. These three theories will be used to create the questionnaire instrument for quantitative research and also to sequence questions for respondents in qualitative research. Honneth's confession theory will be used to understand the language of these confessions. Griffith's addiction theory will be used to determine whether addiction occurs when respondents use social media.

Research by Zhao (Zhao, 2021) entitled "The impact of social media use types and social media addiction on subjective well-being of college students: A comparative analysis of addicted and non-addicted students." The results of this study suggest that social media use has a significant impact on students' mental health. Those who use social media for entertainment will experience more addiction than those who use social media for socializing. This study obtained data from 370 students at various universities in Anhui Province, China.

The subsequent research was conducted by Afacan and Ozbek (Afacan & Ozbek, 2019), entitled "Investigation of Social Media Addiction of High School Students." The subjects studied in this study were 596 students from three different high schools in Kirsehir, Turkey. The results of this study indicate that the level of addiction among the subjects was low. They only used social

media to enjoy it, relieve loneliness, and forget the negative things in their lives. Next is research conducted by Simsek et al., (Simsek et al., 2019) entitled "A Comparative Study on Social Media Addiction of High School and University Students." The results of this study showed that the level of addiction experienced by high school and university students was moderate. Being a student or a college student did not indicate a different level of addiction. The sample for this study consisted of 700 people, all of whom were high school and college students. The subsequent research is from Köse & Doğan (Köse & Doğan, 2019), entitled "The Relationship between Social Media Addiction and Self-Esteem among Turkish University Students." The results of this study indicate a negative relationship between self-confidence and social media addiction. Lower self-confidence negatively impacts social media addiction. The sample for this study consisted of 325 students from three universities during the 2016-2017 academic year. The following study, conducted by Aslan and Yasar (Aslan & Yasar, 2020), is entitled "Measuring Social Media Addiction Among University Students." The results of this study indicate that 90% of the students in the study sample are addicted to social media. This is due to their daily use of social media for more than four hours. The study sample consisted of 675 students who used more than one social media application. Several previous studies have shown that social media use can be addictive. These studies only focused on the duration of social media use, the effects of social media addiction, and the impact of social media addiction on the user's mental health. This study aims to examine the relationship between language used to acknowledge addiction and feelings of addiction in social media use, and whether this language contributes to feelings of addiction.

METHODOLOGY

The research method employed in this study is a mixed-methods approach. Based on research by Askun and Cizel (Askun & Cizel, 2020), "Mixed methods research is a research design with philosophical assumptions and a research method." Creswell and Clark (2007), as cited in Askun and Cizel (Askun & Cizel, 2020), also stated that "The main antecedent is the combined use of qualitative-quantitative data to ensure that the research problem is better understood than any other method used alone." This aligns with the findings of Creswell and Poth (2016) in their article on A. Labrador and O. Alderite (A. Labrador & O. Alderite, 2020) which states that "The purpose of this kind of research is that both quantitative and qualitative research, in combination, provide a better understanding of a research problem or issue than either research approach alone." This means that mixed methods are used to gain a deeper understanding of research that incorporates more than one research method, such as quantitative or qualitative. This is because both research methods have their weaknesses when used individually, as stated by Tobi and Kampen (2018) in the Almeida article (Almeida, 2018) states that "Therefore, it is expected to follow a methodology that not only responds to complex problems, but also aligns the preferences of researchers in multidisciplinary fields." Quantitative and qualitative methods cannot always solve or discuss complex problems, and not all fields can utilize both quantitative and qualitative methods, particularly when a combination of more than one field is involved. Greene (2006) on Almeida's article (Almeida, 2018)" defines the mixed methods concept as mixed method inquiry is an approach to investigating the social world that ideally involves more than one methodological tradition and thus more than one way of knowing." Another, more complete and comprehensive definition comes from Cresswell & Clark (2011), which is also in Almeida's article (Almeida, 2018), states that "mixed methods research is a research design (or methodology) in which the researcher collects, analyzes, and mixes (integrates or connects) both quantitative and qualitative data in a single study or a multiphase program of inquiry." The use of a single research method is not always able to resolve or answer the phenomenon or problem being discussed. Sometimes, it is necessary to use both research methods to obtain a stronger answer to the topic being studied. The mixed methods design used in this study is explanatory. Things that were used to compile the recognition theory instrument Honneth as follows

Table1. Honneth's recognition theory

Forms of relating to self	Forms of recognition	Forms of disrespect	Components of personality

Self-Confidence	Parent secure attachment, love, and care	Neglect, abuse, and emotional neglect	Physical integrity & psychological damage
Self-respect	Legal rights	Violation of legal rights, civil and human rights, and employment rights	Social integrity is treated as an object
Self-esteem	Community of practice, respect & solidarity	Bullying, ignoring, excluding, constant negative feedback	Honor, dignity,

Based on the explanation above, Sianipar (Sianipar, 2025) has produced an instrument adaptation that the author used as a measuring tool for this research.

Griffiths' addiction theory instrument, used in compiling the questionnaire, was distributed using an instrument compiled and carried out by Khairun and Hakim (Khairun & Hakim, 2021). In their research, entitled "*Pengembangan Instrumen Adiksi Media Sosial Instagram Remaja.*" Table of the instrument is

Table 2. Griffiths' addiction theory by Khairun and Hakim(Khairun & Hakim, 2021)

Variables	Indicator
Media Addiction Social	Saliency (importance)
	<i>Mood modification (mood changes)</i>
	<i>Tolerance</i>
	<i>Withdrawal Symptoms</i>
	<i>Conflict</i>

This instrument were tested for validity and reliability because the subjects used in Khairun & Hakim's research differ from those used in the author's research. Khairun & Hakim conducted this research on eighth-grade students of a junior high school in Serang City, Banten.

For quantitative research, the population consisted of adolescents aged 17 and adults aged up to 40 who lived or worked in Jakarta and its surroundings. According to Sugiono (2014), in the article by Suriani et al., (Suriani et al., 2023), a population is a location where respondents meet the criteria and qualities desired by the researcher, allowing them to be studied and sampled to meet the research data needs. This population can be humans or animals, as long as they meet the criteria and qualities sought by the researcher.

A sample was drawn from this population using the snowball sampling technique. According to Suriani et al., (Suriani et al., 2023), Snowball sampling is a technique for obtaining a sample that is initially small but then grows as a result of the distribution of the questionnaire. This sampling can be considered a failure if no new participants are recruited or if participants show no interest in completing the questionnaire (Parker et al., 2019). To prevent this from happening, limitations were imposed on this snowball sampling.

This research will use two data collection techniques. The first technique was use a questionnaire. The second was use interviews. Both techniques were supplemented by documentation. Based on Wade & Travis (2017), in Khairun & Hakim research (Khairun & Hakim, 2021) (2021), a questionnaire is a list or collection of written questions that must be answered in writing. The questions in the questionnaire are based on the instruments mentioned above, presented in the form of a closed questionnaire.

An interview is a question-and-answer activity between the interviewer and the interviewee about the problem being researched, where the interviewer aims to obtain perceptions, attitudes, thought patterns, and information from the interviewee that are relevant to the problem being researched (Rosmita, 2018). Through interviews, researchers can obtain information that cannot be obtained through other data collection methods, such as observation. The interview method used in this study is a structured approach, utilizing guidelines provided by respondents in a previously completed questionnaire.

Documentation serves as a data source to supplement research data, encompassing written sources, videos, images (photos), and monumental works, all of which provide valuable information for the research process. Gunawan (2013), as cited in Rosmita (Rosmita, 2018), Documentation studies complement the use of observation and interview methods. Research results will be more credible if supported by documents. Documentation in this study was used to gather information through various documents related to the research problem.

Sugiono (2011) in Rosmita's writing (Rosmita, 2018), mixed methods research designs are divided into three categories: sequential explanatory design, sequential exploratory design, and concurrent triangulation design. This study employed a sequential explanatory design, which involves collecting and analyzing quantitative data, followed by qualitative analysis.

According to Creswell & Plano-Clark (2011), as cited in Yusfiarto's article (Yusfiarto, 2023), sequential explanatory design involves the sequential collection of both quantitative and qualitative data. The first stage is carried out using quantitative methods to objectively measure the phenomenon or variable being studied. Then, the next stage, or the second stage, is carried out using qualitative methods to gain a deeper understanding of the phenomenon being studied.

Therefore, in data analysis techniques, this design places more emphasis on quantitative data. Sequential exploratory design is a sequential combination of qualitative and quantitative data collection methods. The first stage is conducted using qualitative methods, followed by the next stage, which employs quantitative methods. Concurrent triangulation design is a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, carried out by mixing the two equally, with a 50% quantitative and 50% qualitative approach. In analyzing the data quantitatively, the author used a simple linear regression test on the results of a questionnaire regarding the influence of recognition language on social media use. After the calculation results indicated reliable and normal data, the author conducted a simple linear regression test. Based on the article by Harizahayu et al., (Harizahayu et al., 2023), it is stated that "The purpose of linear regression analysis is to determine whether the relationship between the independent and dependent variables is positive or negative and to predict the value of the dependent variable if the value of the independent variable increases or decreases." The purpose of this analysis is to determine whether a relationship exists between variables, whether the relationship is positive or negative, and whether the value of the variable increases or decreases. "The simple linear regression model is the simplest regression model with only one independent variable" (Wibowo, 2022).

Meanwhile, in analyzing qualitative data, interviews are conducted interactively and continuously until the data are saturated. Activities in qualitative data analysis include data reduction, data presentation, and data verification. According to Sugiyono (2014), in the article by Alfero et al., (Alfero et al., 2022), it is stated that reducing data involves summarizing, selecting the main points, focusing on important points, and identifying themes and patterns.

In reducing data, researchers must refer to the objectives to be achieved in a study. By performing data reduction, the existing data will provide a clearer picture, making it easier for researchers to collect further data. Sugiyono (2014), as cited in Alfero et al., (Alfero et al., 2022), states that presenting data involves presenting a collection of organized information that enables drawing conclusions and taking action. By displaying data, researchers will be able to more easily understand what is happening and plan further work based on their understanding.

Verifying data or drawing conclusions is the culmination of a series of data analysis; therefore, it is a good idea to review a conclusion by re-verifying the notes from the research and looking for patterns, themes, relationship models, and similarities to conclude. Sugiyono (2014), as cited in Alfero et al., (Alfero et al., 2022), stated that the conclusion could be a description, a picture of an object that was previously unclear but becomes clearer after research, a causal or interactive relationship, or a hypothesis or theory.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The questionnaire was a closed-ended questionnaire, where respondents could only answer with the available options. The questionnaire was administered to 97 respondents aged 17-40, living or working in Jakarta, who were either studying or working, and had social media accounts. To analyze the data in this study, the questionnaire results were subjected to a simple linear regression test. Simple linear regression test requirements:

1. Valid and reliable
2. Normal and linear

Basis for decision making:

Decision making in simple linear regression testing can refer to two things, namely:

1. Comparing the significance value with the probability value of 0.05
 - If the significance value is <0.05 , it means that variable X affects variable Y.
 - If the significance value is >0.05 , it means that variable X does not affect variable Y.
2. Compare the calculated t value with the t value in the t table.
 - If the calculated t-value is greater than the t-table value, it means that variable X affects variable Y.
 - If the calculated t value $<$ t table, it means that variable X does not affect variable Y.

The simple linear regression formula is as follows:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Information:

Y = Dependent variable (bound variable)

X = Independent variable (free variable)

a = Constant (value of Y when X = 0)

b = Regression coefficient (positive or negative effect)

If the output has been obtained, the next step is to look up the t-table value. The formula for finding the t-table is:

$$\text{Value } a / 2 = 0.005 / 2 = 0.025$$

$$\text{Degrees of freedom (df)} = n - 2 = 97 - 2 = 95$$

The value is 0.025; 95, then we look at the distribution of the t-table values

d.f	t _{0.10}	t _{0.05}	t _{0.025}	t _{0.01}	t _{0.005}
61	1.296	1.671	2.000	2.390	2.659
62	1.296	1.671	1.999	2.389	2.659
63	1.296	1.670	1.999	2.389	2.658
64	1.296	1.670	1.999	2.388	2.657
65	1.296	1.670	1.998	2.388	2.657
66	1.295	1.670	1.998	2.387	2.656
67	1.295	1.670	1.998	2.387	2.655
68	1.295	1.670	1.997	2.386	2.655
69	1.295	1.669	1.997	2.386	2.654
70	1.295	1.669	1.997	2.385	2.653
71	1.295	1.669	1.996	2.385	2.653
72	1.295	1.669	1.996	2.384	2.652
73	1.295	1.669	1.996	2.384	2.651
74	1.295	1.668	1.995	2.383	2.651
75	1.295	1.668	1.995	2.383	2.650
76	1.294	1.668	1.995	2.382	2.649
77	1.294	1.668	1.994	2.382	2.649
78	1.294	1.668	1.994	2.381	2.648
79	1.294	1.668	1.994	2.381	2.647
80	1.294	1.667	1.993	2.380	2.647
81	1.294	1.667	1.993	2.380	2.646
82	1.294	1.667	1.993	2.379	2.645
83	1.294	1.667	1.992	2.379	2.645
84	1.294	1.667	1.992	2.378	2.644
85	1.294	1.666	1.992	2.378	2.643
86	1.293	1.666	1.991	2.377	2.643
87	1.293	1.666	1.991	2.377	2.642
88	1.293	1.666	1.991	2.376	2.641
89	1.293	1.666	1.990	2.376	2.641
90	1.293	1.666	1.990	2.375	2.640
91	1.293	1.665	1.990	2.374	2.639
92	1.293	1.665	1.989	2.374	2.639
93	1.293	1.665	1.989	2.373	2.638
94	1.293	1.665	1.989	2.373	2.637
95	1.293	1.665	1.988	2.372	2.637

Picture 1. t table

So, the t table value is 1.988

Variables Entered/Removed

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Recognition	.	Enter

- a. Dependent Variable: Addiction
- b. All requested variables entered.

Picture 2. variables entered/removed.

Output part 1 (variables entered/removed)

The table above explains the variables entered and the method used. The variables entered above are the recognition language variable as the independent variable and the addiction variable as the dependent variable, and the method used is the enter method.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	.642a	.413	.406	10.14448

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Recognition
- b. Dependent Variable: Addiction

Picture 3. model summary

Output part 2 (Model Summary)

The table above explains the magnitude of the correlation/relationship value (R), which is 0.642. From this output, the coefficient of determination (R Square) is 0.413, which means that the influence of the independent variable (language of recognition) on the dependent variable (addiction nature) is 41.3%.

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6868.479	1	6868.479	66,742	.000b
	Residual	9776.490	95	102,910		
	Total	16644.969	96			

a. Dependent Variable: Addiction
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Recognition

Picture 4. ANOVA

Output 3 (ANOVA)

Based on the output above, it is known that the calculated F value is 66.742, with a significance level of 0.000, where $0.000 < 0.05$. Therefore, the regression model can be used to predict addiction variables, or in other words, there is an influence of the recognition language variable (X) on the addiction variable (Y).

Coefficientsa

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	15,179	9.107		1,667	.099
	Recognition	1,286	.157	.642	8,170	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Addiction

Picture 5. Coefficients

Output 4 (coefficients)

It is known that the recognition language value (a) is 15.179 while the addiction value (b/ b/regression coefficient) is 1.286, so the regression equation can be written as follows.

$$Y = a + bX$$

$$Y = 15.179 + 1.286X$$

Interpretation:

1. The constant value shows a value of 15.179, meaning that if there is a change in the independent variable (the value of X is 0), then the value of the dependent variable, Y, is 15.179
2. The regression coefficient value for variable X (language of recognition) is 1.286, which is positive; therefore, it can be said that the direction of the influence of variable X on Y is also positive. If the language of recognition increases by one value, then addiction will increase by 1.286, and this applies when experiencing a decline.

Decision-making in simple regression testing

1. Based on the significance value.

From the coefficients table, a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ was obtained, indicating that the recognition variable (X) has a significant effect on the addiction variable (Y).

2. Based on the t value.

It is known that the cat-valued t value, which is greater than the t-table value is greater than the t-table value. Therefore, 1.988, so it can be concluded that the recognition variable (X) affects the addiction variable (Y)

Residuals Statistics

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation	N
Predicted Value	66.5998	124.4483	89.1031	8.45853	97
Residual	-27.31027	30.54764	.00000	10.09150	97
Std. Predicted Value	-2,660	4,179	.000	1,000	97
Std. Residual	-2,692	3,011	.000	.995	97

a. Dependent Variable: Addiction

Picture 6. Residual Statistics

Picture7. Histogram (Regression Standardized Residual)

Picture 8. Histogram (Observed Cum Prob)

From the questionnaire distribution, it was found that the language of recognition influences the emergence of addictive traits in social media users in Jakarta and the surrounding areas. This is evident from the results of a simple regression test. Based on the significance value, the language of recognition, in this case variable X, influences the addictive traits, in this case variable Y. Then, based on the t-value, the language of recognition, as variable X, influences the addictive traits, as variable Y. This is in line with research conducted

by Fajarni (Fajarni, 2022).

Honeth's quote in Fajarni's article (Fajarni, 2022) mentioning that when placing the dimension of "recognition" as the main one in building social relations, Honeth expressed his belief that prioritizing relations between people rather than actions based on mature goals opens up the possibility for them to express themselves in front of their communication partners just to be accepted by others and increase social relations.

Based on the results above, it can be concluded that the language of recognition from others has led social media users in Jakarta to become addicted to using social media. This could be the reason why the growth of social media users is becoming increasingly massive, and their activities are becoming increasingly unfocused due to the desire for recognition from other users.

This aligns with research by Nurwati & S (2016) and an article by Sabekti et al., (Sabekti et al., 2019). The study found that social media is addictive for teenagers; the more active they are on social media, the cooler and more sociable they appear.

What has been highlighted by these social media users is their increasing disregard for what should and should not be posted due to their desire for validation from others. As a result, a sense of addiction is growing among social media users. As social media users in Jakarta increasingly seek validation, their addiction to social media also increases.

This also aligns with research by Sifa and Sawitri (Sifa & Sawitri, 2018), who examined the relationship between Instagram social media addiction and self-regulation? The results showed a negative relationship between addiction levels and self-regulation, where higher levels of self-regulation lower the potential for addiction, and vice versa. If social media users can control themselves, they can control what they post on social media, thereby reducing the addictive nature of social media use. This can also happen vice versa.

This research is a mixed-methods study with an explanatory design. This study employs qualitative research to interpret the findings of previously conducted quantitative research. In qualitative research, the researcher chose to use the interview method with one of the respondents from the questionnaire that had been distributed. The selected respondent is **Praz Teguh**.

Praz Teguh is an Indonesian stand-up comedian and also a YouTube activist. His YouTube channel, **Tuah Kreasi**, has 1.86 million followers. On other social media platforms, such as Instagram, Praz Teguh has 2.1 million users who follow his account. For TikTok, Praz Teguh has 1.1 million followers on his TikTok account. Praz Teguh is also known to the general public as a reliable podcaster or podcast host. One of the famous podcasts where Praz Teguh is an interviewer is Close The Door, which Deddy Corbuzier owns.

Although Praz Teguh is quite active on social media, he has a more selective view regarding its use. For Praz, social media is not the primary place to seek recognition, but rather a means to share work or things of real value. However, he acknowledges that most social media users use it as a primary place to seek recognition.

This aligns with research by Nurwati & S (2016) and an article by Sabekti et al., (Sabekti et al., 2019). Some argue that social media is addictive for teenagers, suggesting that the more active they are, the cooler and more sociable they become. Social media offers a variety of features, allowing users to freely share their experiences. Praz Teguh disagrees with the current state of social media, feeling that social media fame can sometimes be immature, especially when it lacks direct interaction or tangible work behind it.

Praz does not care about how often he posts, unless it is for professional purposes, such as advertising. He sees social media as a tool for promotion, nothing more. He is limiting himself due to the many negative comments he has seen on social media lately. He believes negative comments on social media can harm his mental health, so he prefers to limit his posts and avoid drama or sarcasm.

Praz's statement aligns with research by Kuss & Griffiths (2011) in an article by Santoso et al., (Santoso et al., 2022) The article states that the rapid increase in social media use, particularly regarding the increasing amount of time people spend online, has led some to claim that excessive social media use may be addictive to some individuals.

Excessive internet and mass media use can have both physical and mental impacts. Excessive social media use not only has negative consequences, such as seeing negative comments about anything, especially oneself, but can also lead to addiction. As noted in research by Sakinah et al., individuals who spend a significant amount of time on social media can develop dependency or addiction. (Sakinah et al., 2019). To avoid problems in the future, Praz Teguh stated that if there are disturbing comments, especially those related to his family, he will not hesitate to block them to protect his family's well-being.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that the desire for recognition from others has led social media users in Jakarta to become addicted to social media use. This finding was further reinforced by an interview with one of the respondents, Praz Teguh, a social media activist in Indonesia and a celebrity. Praz Teguh acknowledged that many social media users use it as a platform to

seek recognition. However, he maintains a more limited social media presence, specifically in terms of the frequency of his posts. He views social media primarily as a promotional tool. He frequently posts on social media about work-related matters.

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Cite this Article: Sianipar, Y.O., Alvina, T., Tambunan, S.L. (2025). The Effect of Recognition Language on Addictive Nature in The Use of Social Media. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 8(8), pp. 4166-4178. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i8-24>